

Polish Geological Society
Faculty of Geology, University of Warsaw
Institute of Palaeobiology, Polish Academy of Sciences
Polish Geological Institute – National Research Institute

10th Baltic Stratigraphic Conference

Chęciny, 12–14 September 2017

Abstracts and Field Guide

Edited by Anna Żylińska

Faculty of Geology, University of Warsaw

Warszawa 2017

Givetian vertebrate assemblages from the Burtnieki Regional Stage (Devonian) of the East Baltic

Alexander O. Ivanov¹, Dasha V. Pinakhina¹, Vadim N. Glinskiy¹ and Ervīns Lukševičs²

¹*Institute of Earth Sciences, Saint Petersburg State University, Universitetskaya nab. 7/9, 199034 Sankt Petersburg, Russia; IvanovA-Paleo@yandex.ru; acanthodasha@gmail.com; vadim.glinskiy@gmail.com*

²*Department of Geology, University of Latvia, Raiņa Boulevard 19, Riga LV-1586, Latvia; ervins.luksevis@lu.lv*

The Givetian vertebrate assemblages of the Burtnieki Regional Stage (RS) were analyzed from the localities of the East Baltic: the Veczemji cliff on the Baltic sea coast in north-western Latvia; the Karksi exposure in southern Estonia; the Kemka River, Domanov Creek, Nesterkovo exposure and the Novinka quarry in the south-western part of the Sankt Petersburg Region, Russia. These assemblages include diverse psammosteid agnathans, placoderm, acanthodian, chondrichthyan, sarcopterygian and actinopterygian fishes (see Table 1).

The psammosteids are represented in those assemblages by five genera: *Pycnosteus*, *Ganosteus*, *Tartuosteus*, *Psammolepis*, and *Psammosteus*. The *Pycnosteus tuberculatus* psammosteid Zone corresponds to the Härma and Koorkiila members of the Burtnieki RS, and the *Psammolepis abavica* Zone – to the Abava Member. The Karksi and Novinka localities yield the most diverse psammosteid taxa. *Pycnosteus tuberculatus* occurs in all sites except Veczemji and the upper level of Novinka. *Psammolepis abavica* has been found in Veczemji, the upper level of Novinka and Nesterkovo. Both index species are recorded in one level only in Nesterkovo. A new species of *Psammolepis* was reported from the Karksi and Domanov Creek localities.

The remains of placoderms are abundant in the Kemka, Domanov and Novinka localities. The Burtnieki RS corresponds to the *Asterolepis dellei* placoderm Zone. The index species occurs in all localities apart Nesterkovo. The placoderms are very rare in the Veczemji locality but they are numerous and taxonomically diverse in Karksi, Kemka, Domanov and Novinka. The remains of *Actinolepis magna* and *Homostius latus* dominate in the assemblages. *Byssacanthus* frequently found in the Arukula RS is rarely recorded in the Burtnieki RS.

The scarcely occurring remains of chondrichthyans in the Middle Devonian of the Baltic Region are represented by two taxa, *Karksiodus mirus* and *Karksilepis parva*, and reported from the Veczemji, Karksi, Kemka and Novinka localities.

The most taxonomically diverse group of vertebrates in the Burtnieki assemblages are acanthodians. Abundant acanthodians have been found in Karksi. The scales of "*Acanthodes*", *Ptychodictyon sulcatum* Gross, *Cheiracanthus brevicostatus* Gross and *Diplacanthus crassissimus* (Duff) are very frequent in that locality. The acanthodian remains are numerous in the Veczemji and Novinka localities but their taxonomic diversity is smaller than in Karksi. The Domanov locality contains numerous fin spines but the scales are not recorded. The *Diplacanthus gravis* acanthodian Zone traditionally corresponds to the Arukula and Burtnieki RS. However, a recent study demonstrates considerable differences between the acanthodian assemblages from those of the Burtnieki RS. *Diplacanthus* cf. *D. crassissimus*, *Gomphonchus*? n. sp., *Isodendracanthus* n. sp. and *Rhadinacanthus* n. sp. are characteristic only of the Burtnieki RS. *Nostolepis gaujensis* Valiukevičius known from the Gauja RS appeared already in the Burtnieki RS.

Sarcopterygians, especially osteolepiforms and porolepiforms, are common in almost all localities. The rare remains of strunniiform sarcopterygians occur in Veczemji and Karksi. Sporadic remains of actinopterygian *Cheirolepis* sp. were reported from the Karksi and Kemka localities.

The taxonomic diversity of the assemblages from the Burtnieki RS is considerably higher in contrast to what was considered before. Many taxa are widely distributed in the East Baltic area.

Table 1. Distribution of vertebrate taxa in the localities of the Burtnieki Regional Stage.

	Vertebrate taxa	Vz	Kr	Km-1	DR 1	Ns	Nv-1	Nv-2
Psammosteids	<i>Pycnosteus tuberculatus</i> (Rohon)		x	x	x	x	x	
	<i>Ganosteus stellatus</i> Rohon		x			x	x	x
	<i>Tartuosteus maximus</i> Mark-Kurik	x	x		x		x	x
	<i>Psammolepis abavica</i> Mark-Kurik	x				x		x
	<i>Psammolepis</i> n. sp.		x		x			
	<i>Psammosteus bergi</i> (Obruchev)	x	x	x	x		x	x
Placoderms	<i>Actinolepis magna</i> Mark-Kurik		x	x sp.	x sp.		x	x
	<i>Homostius latus</i> Asmuss		x	x	x sp.	x	x	x
	<i>Heterostius</i> sp.			x		x	x	
	<i>Dickosteus</i> sp.		x	x	x		x	x
	<i>Asterolepis dellei</i> Gross	x cf.	x	x cf.	x		x	x
	<i>Byssacanthus</i> sp.				x			x cf.
	<i>Ptyctodontiformes</i> indet.						x	x
Acanthodians	<i>Cheiracanthus brevicostatus</i> Gross	x	x					
	<i>Cheiracanthus latus</i> Egerton	x	x					x
	<i>Cheiracanthus longicostatus</i> Gross			x				
	<i>Diplacanthus gravis</i> Valiukevičius	x aff.						x
	<i>Diplacanthus crassissimus</i> (Duff)	x	x					x
	<i>Diplacanthus tenuistriatus</i> Traquair	x	x cf.					
	<i>Gomphonchus?</i> n. sp.		x					
	<i>Isodendracanthus</i> n. sp.	x						
	<i>Nostolepis gaujensis</i> Valiukevičius		x	x ?				
	<i>Ptychodictyon rimosum</i> Gross		x					
	<i>Ptychodictyon sulcatum</i> Gross	x	x	x				x
	<i>Rhadinacanthus</i> n. sp.		x					x
	<i>Rhadinacanthus longispinus</i> (Agassiz)	x	x	x	x			x
	<i>Archaeacanthus?</i> sp.			x				
“ <i>Acanthodes</i> ” sp.	x	x	x	x			x	
Ch	<i>Karksiodus mirus</i> Ivanov & Märss		x	x				x
	<i>Karksilepis parva</i> Märss	x	x					
Sarcopt	<i>Glyptolepis</i> sp.		x	x	x		x	x
	Porolepiformes indet.	x	x	x	x		x	x
	Strunniiformes indet.	x	x					
	<i>Gyroptychius</i> sp.		x				x	x
	Osteolepiformes indet.	x		x	x	x	x	x
Ac	<i>Cheirolepis</i> sp.		x	x				

Abbreviations. Locality: Vz – Veczemji cliff, Kr – Karksi exposure, Km-1 – Kemka River, DR 1 – Domanov Creek, Ns – Nesterkovo exposure, Nv-1 and Nv-2 – lower and upper levels in the Novinka quarry. Group of taxa: A – Actinopterygians, Ch – Chondrichthyans, Sarcopt – Sarcopterygians